

Specialized Cutting Technique for QFN Leadframe Semiconductor Package

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Abstract—The paper presents a specialized cutting technique for package singulation without using the conventional mechanical blade.

Keywords— Package singulation; cutting technique; QFN.

I. BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

- Package singulation process is one of the known sawing techniques on QFN (quad flat no-lead) leadframe semiconductor manufacturing to separate the encapsulated leadframe into individual units
- Conventional package sawing or singulation process uses a mechanical blade to cut through the metal and mold material according to defined package size of the product

Fig. 1. Singulation of individual unit from the encapsulated leadframe strip.

- Conventional package singulation technique comes with some process/assembly related rejections:

- Metal burrs
- Un-cut
- Shallow cut
- Delamination due to singulation
- Topside chippings

- Package chip-out was evident on Device Z with measurement greater than the specification limit of 125µm

Fig. 2. Device Z topside chip-out.

- Parameter optimization, blade selection and evaluation, and ensuring planarity and calibration can help mitigate the package chip-out, but still cannot be totally eliminated due to the degradation of the mechanical blade

II. DESIGN SOLUTION

- A specialized cutting technique for QFN assembly is introduced without the use of mechanical blade to singulate or separate the unit individually
- The process is realized through modification of the mold tool design, maximizing the deflash process, and employing chemical etching process

Fig. 3. Specialized cutting technique for QFN leadframe semiconductor package.

- The specialized cutting technique is an advancement in QFN technology, supporting assembly yield improvement and cost